

Title of email: Collaboration on TOXOSOURCES European project: Research on *Toxoplasma gondii* presence in RTA salads.

To whom it may concern,

TOXOSOURCES (*Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified; <https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/>) is a Joint Research Project within the H2020 One Health European Joint Programme. This activity has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 773830. TOXOSOURCES aims to address the research question – What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *T. gondii* infection? – following the research needs identified by the European stakeholders, ECDC and EFSA. TOXOSOURCES is a strong consortium with altogether 20 EJP-partners, and RTE-production is represented in its Interest Group. *Toxoplasma gondii* is protozoan parasite, a highly prioritized but so far not systematically controlled zoonotic foodborne pathogen in Europe and globally. Consumption of fresh produce is one of the possible routes of *T. gondii* transmission to humans hardly explored up to date. Thus, in this context it is timely to get knowledge on the presence of *T. gondii* in RTE products. As part of the TOXOSOURCES Work Packages 2 and 3 (WP2 and WP3), we are conducting a survey on the trade and consumption of fresh produce/vegetables within the European Economic Area. We use the results to evaluate the possible role of fresh produce as source of *T. gondii* infections (quantitative microbiological risk assessment), and to design a sampling strategy for a multi-center study investigating fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat Salads) for presence of *T. gondii* oocysts. We would highly appreciate your cooperation in this matter and let us know the most appropriate contact person in your company. First, we would need a reply to an on line survey. Please, find the link herein (<https://surrey.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/toxosources-rte-product-trade-and-distribution-chain>) and feel free to fill in it in your native language. Second, we offer the opportunity to test your products. Thus, your company will be among the first companies to get their products tested, for free and by top specialists. An online questionnaire (link to site) has been designed to collect information to identify the most frequently sold fresh produce (particularly fourth range products) in each country and obtain some information on the processing measures/steps that may influence the safety of the final product. The company name and the data of origin will be kept confidential. Collected data will be used for legitimate research purposes only under TOXOSOURCES context and will be not disclosed to third parties. We will ensure confidential storage of data. Those companies willing to participate will have access to the on line summary of the results obtained that will be available via the TOXOSOURCES project page.

Please, do not hesitate to get in touch with us (gemaga@ucm.es; r.calero@ucm.es; m.betson@surrey.ac.uk) if you have any further questions. We would be very grateful if you could complete the spreadsheet by the end of August 2020.

Many thanks for your participation in this WP3 task 2 (WP3-T2).

Best wishes,

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